

Production networks in the creative and cultural sector and multilevel governance in local and regional ecosystems

Authors

Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway and Marc Pradel

30 May 2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

This report is part of the CICERONE project, which has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program under grant agreement no. 822778.

The project is conducted by

The CICERONE project is coordinated by the Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research (AISSR) at the University of Amsterdam, which is located at

Nieuwe Achtergracht 166
1018 WV Amsterdam
The Netherlands

info@cicerone-project.eu
www.cicerone-project.eu

Disclaimer

This publication reflects the authors' views only. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information that it contains.

This report is to be cited as

Pareja-Eastaway, M. and Pradel, M. (2023) *Production networks in the cultural and creative sector and multilevel governance in local and regional ecosystems* (CICERONE deliverable D6.2) DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/8098807>

Authors

Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway and Marc Pradel are both Associate Professors at the University of Barcelona, Spain. Pareja-Eastaway is Associate Professor at the Department of Economics. Pradel at the Department of Sociology.

Credits

This report is openly published under the Creative Common license CC-BY, which requires giving credit to the authors and the CICERONE project when being reused.

Policy frameworks for production networks in the creative and cultural sector: an international perspective

Project name	Creative Industries Cultural Economy Production Network
Project acronym	CICERONE
Grant agreement ID	822778
Deliverable number	D6.2
Responsible partner	University of Barcelona
Work package	<p>The CICERONE project consists of seven work packages (WPs). This report is part of WP6. Building a capacity to engage is what this WP is essentially about.</p> <p>WP6 is mainly rooted in theoretical work (WP1) and a large-scale empirical case study research (WP2) of actually existing production networks across eight different industries of the cultural and creative sector (CCS). While WP1 focused on the question of how to apply the concept of global production networks on the CCS, WP2 applied this framework with the purpose generating an in-depth understanding of key linkages and mechanisms within CCS networks and how these linkages and mechanisms relate to context-dependent variables. Drawing on both these sources, WP6 explores a network based policy framework that may contribute to enhancing policy support for the cultural and creative sectors.</p> <p>WP6 consist of four deliverables. D6.1 makes the case for a network-based approach to the CCS. D6.2 focuses on where networks get embedded at local, regional and national scales, why this matters, and how policy can address these. D6.3 studies inputs to policy from the sector itself, providing an overview of CCS representation at EU level. D6.4 summarizes many of the project's implications for policy towards the CCS.</p> <p>All the deliverables from the CICERONE project are publicly disclosed on the project's website www.cicerone-project.eu and through its Zenodo community on https://zenodo.org/communities/cicerone-h2020.</p>

Table of contents

INTRODUCTION	5
1. INTRODUCTION TO LOCAL AND REGIONAL ECOSYSTEMS AND THEIR EMBEDDEDNESS IN NATIONAL FRAMEWORKS	13
1.1 The role of ‘local’ and ‘regional’ ecosystems in global production networks	13
1.2 The subsidiarity principle and the embeddedness of the local ecosystem in higher (national, European, global) scales	15
1.3 Why and how the global production network is dependent on the socio-institutional context for policy-making?	16
1.4 How the spatial footprint of global production networks is relevant for policy recommendations/establishment of policy frameworks?	17
2. MULTILEVEL POLICY CHALLENGES MANIFESTED IN THE LOCAL AND REGIONAL ECOSYSTEMS THROUGH A PRODUCTION NETWORK APPROACH.....	20
2.1 Multilevel policy challenges and how they are affected by diverse characteristics of the cultural and creative sector	20
2.2 Global production network phases and strategic coupling in multilevel policy frameworks	23
3. USING THE TYPOLOGY: CASE ILLUSTRATIONS RELATED TO PRODUCTION NETWORK TYPES	29
4. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FROM THE LOCAL ECOSYSTEM IN A MULTILEVEL GOVERNANCE PERSPECTIVE	34
5. SUMMARY OF RESULTS	37
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	40

1. Introduction

Culture is rooted in space and time and so creative and cultural industries are. Creativity and innovation, essential components of the knowledge – creative economy, are situated in epistemic communities and concrete spaces, both local and global, which are networked and embedded in a set of formal and informal dependencies and relations (Jeffcutt, 2004; Scott, 2004). However, space acquires a new dimension in a globalised world. Global Production Networks (GPNs) connect different territories thereby shape them and, in turn, are shaped by them (Coe and Yeung, 2015). Policymaking is not isolated from the interdependencies between organisations and actors at varied spheres and cannot be delimited. GPN is useful as a method to design and promote efficient policymaking.

Research on the cultural and creative sector (CCS) has amply shown the relevance of urban agglomerations in the production of creative and cultural products and services (Jeffcutt & Pratt, 2002; Scott, 1999). Literature has mainly focused on clustering and agglomeration of creative industries and has shown the relevance of local institutional contexts in generating environments or ecosystems formed by actors, places, and spaces in which the rise of creative and cultural industries takes place.

Instead of focusing on territories *per se*, the GPN approach concentrates on the relations of different firms at a global scale that generate competitive dynamics. Nevertheless, this perspective includes the role of local and regional institutional contexts influencing the dynamic interactions within global production networks. Following Coe and Yeung (N. M. Coe & Yeung, 2015), the GPN lens allows us to understand how firms, more or less embedded in local ecosystems, connect with global production networks in different ways and how the certain developments of regional economies might also be connected to GPN. This approach uses the term ‘*strategic coupling*’ to describe the different ways in which regional and national economies intersect with GPNs.

The CICERONE project has opted for using a production network approach as its theoretical point of departure and guide our empirical mapping of the production networks. We use the basic components (phases, location, embeddedness, governance) of this framework to unpack CCS activities in a novel way. Instead of concentrating on clusters of cultural and creative activities and creative cities, we look at production networks comprising different phases of production, which can be located in (very) different places each with its own socio-cultural and institutional context, and we try to assess how these networks are governed. By explicitly including archiving as a distinct phase and thereby making our network approach more cyclical, we highlight the possibilities of feedback, learning and innovation through hybridisation in the CCS. As the GPN perspective is first and foremost “a heuristic framework for interpreting the evolving multi-scalar geographies of the global economy” (Coe, 2015: 486), we

can use, tweak and combine these basic components in ways that fit our main purpose of devising a new policy framework for the CCS.

The departure point of this report is that economic development of a region results from the aggregation of individual trajectories of firms upgrading or downgrading their position in global production networks. Firms can range from being very much isolated from such networks to becoming the core of them. This is obviously affecting local economic development as some forms of coupling and capture of value come to dominate at the regional level. Coe et al. (2014) highlight the need to ‘strategically coupling’ both, the global production network and regional assets as an interface that ‘... is crucially mediated by a range of institutional activities across different spatial scales. (...) regional development depends on the ability of this coupling mechanism to facilitate processes of value creation, enhancement and capture’ (N. Coe et al., 2004, p. 481) (see Figure 1, next page).

Figure 1. Global Production Networks and ‘strategic coupling’ with regional assets and institutions

Source: Based on (N. M. Coe et al., 2004)

Individual firms attempt to couple to GPNs in different ways, but the institutional context, the trajectory of forms of strategic coupling and the policies produced generate specific conditions for coupling. Besides, firms are not the only actors playing a role in this process of coupling: public administrations at different levels and institutional actors can clearly influence such processes.

Territories, understood as a sum of actors with different representativity and power, can choose to connect with certain global production network as a strategic objective. Territories can also strategically decouple from an existing GPN for different reasons, for instance, to develop local actors

in different phases. A city or a region can develop a strategy to host core companies in certain GPNs, or to 'capture' part of the activity of the GPN. Strategic coupling at territorial level can be led by local actors, but it can be the case also that supralocal public and private actors intervene in such strategies (for instance, the national government fostering infrastructures or a powerful private actor landing in the territory and promoting networking with other actors). Besides, the constellation of local institutional actors matters in defining these strategies of strategic coupling. The role of public administrations and institutions, private actors and representatives of civil society are key in the definition of economic develop strategies and the ways in which companies connect to GPNs. Historical trajectories (path dependency) are also relevant as they generate identity and influence paths and behaviours (Pradel-Miquel, 2012).

Thus, beyond analysing the spatial footprint of GPNs as the mere impact of firms in the territory, we focus on which policy approaches and policies foster coupling strategies for CCS, attending to the different typologies of networks constructed in the CICERONE project. Policies and policy approaches at regional and local level are especially relevant in the CCS, as public actors are often enmeshed both in production and consumption of products and services in most of such sectors. The GPN approach allows for analysing policy frameworks from a different lens. As Coe states: *'GPNs do not merely locate in particular places; they both shape, and are shaped by, the institutional and regulatory contexts in which they invest'* (Coe, 2015, p. 489). As Coe underlines, this is especially important for the creative industries, as they are considered cornerstones for local economic development, giving room to policies and fiscal incentives aimed at attracting and growing creative industries.

The European Recovery Agenda after the pandemic considers the CCS as drivers for creation of jobs, growth, social fairness, and sustainable development (European Commission, 2022). CICERONE local environments and case studies provide an innovative perspective that, by departing from a more comprehensive approach on CCS functioning based on the GPN approach, will certainly inspire a new articulation of policymaking by public and non-public actors, by local and global stakeholders and by the involvement of different levels of government. The typology of the global production networks and its embeddedness in a particular local context will provide room for action and intervention of local policies.

To do so, we aim at looking at the local impact (spatial footprint) of those varied networks of organisations with a global scope but locally embedded. We focus on the local impact of the articulation of policies, interventions and actions of the different institutional and non-institutional actors at different tiers of government and scales of intervention. We aim at providing ideas on how policies for CCS can be better designed by attending the involvement of organisations in the local-global dynamic that the GPN analysis offers (See Table 1). Table 1 illustrates the local and non-local manifestations of four dimensions of regional development, that is, firms, labour, technology and institutions. The GPN approach contributes to a better understanding of how these dimensions might be affected by different territorial scales, crucial for a multilevel policy making strategy.

Table 1. Local and non-local forms of different dimensions of regional development

Dimensions	Local manifestations	Non-local forms
Firms	Indigenous SMEs Industrial clusters (creative?) Intra-regional markets Venture capitalists	Global corporations Entrepreneurial subsidies Distant global markets Decentralized business and financial networks
Labour	Skilled and unskilled workers Permanent migrants	Global production networks Skilled experts and technologists Transient migrants
Technology	Spillovers effects Tacit knowledge Infrastructure and assets	Transnational business elites Global standards and practices Intrafirm R&D activities Technological licensing
Institutions	Conventions and norms Growth coalitions Local authorities Development agencies	Strategic alliances Labour and trade unions Business associations National agencies and authorities Inter-institutional alliances Supranational and international organisations

Source: Based on (N. M. Coe et al., 2004)

While CCS research has mostly focused on the sub-national level, studying the agglomeration of activities in the space and how policies can promote this concentration (N. Coe, 2015), the GPN approach provides a dynamic view on how organisations can benefit from a multilevel governance (local, regional, national and supranational) that contribute to their better positioning in the global network. But it also provides an understanding of how the local ecosystem, the city, can also benefit from accommodating the global production network of these sectors at their specific spatial scale. Since the GPN contributes *‘to open-up our understandings of these industries in both functional and geographical terms’* (N. Coe, 2015, p. 487), policy is also revealed to acquire a new potential while following this approach.

This deliverable analyses components and frameworks susceptible/eligible as targets for policy action, co-creation of interventions or reinforcement of already existing of practices at the local ecosystem in relation to the different phases of the GPN (creation, production, exchange, distribution, archive). We will be looking at the spatial footprint in the different phases (clustering of activities, local labour market conditions, characteristics of the local labour supply, education institutions, promotion of entrepreneurs, gatekeepers...) and the governance and established power relations (associations, federations, networks, market structure...) of the different phases at the local ecosystem where the CICERONE case studies of CCIs have been approached. While literature (Braun & Lavanga, 2007; Foord, 2009) has fundamentally focused on the creation phase of CCS, the GPN approach allows us to confront the production dynamics between companies and professionals along the production process, not only in the creation stage. The GPN approach provides a more nuanced perspective to

the connections between different spatial scales. In this frame, local institutional actors and policies must be understood not only as contextual elements facilitating the landing of part of the GPNs but integral elements of the value dynamics of the GPN (Coe, 2015).

The CICERONE fieldwork comprised empirical research on CCI sectors to understand the role of CCIs in the local development of EU countries starting from the configuration and dynamics of their global production networks (GPNs). The methodology was that of case-study analysis, integrating existing literature, secondary data with in-depth investigation through qualitative and quantitative analysis. Thus, the CICERONE empirical research adopted a mixed methods approach of investigation. Case studies benefited from cross country comparison: the different contexts shed light on different dynamics related to economic circumstances, national and local regulatory framework, labour market, local culture and know-how, and so on.

The selection of the case studies was based on the findings of an initial overview, regarding the relationship between the guiding questions and the different organisational structures of the GPN. Six research questions guided the work: Where is value created, accrued and captured? What are the working conditions in various segments of production networks? How much agency do workers have within and across nodes? How, where and by whom knowledge is produced, transferred and used and how is this embedded in the local and national institutional framework? Are there conflicts within networks, or related to it? How do production networks contribute to local economic development?

The rationale behind this report is as follows: we have departed from the CICERONE case studies which reflect a particular organisation of the network (both in terms of governance and spatial footprint) and are inserted in specific local ecosystems characterised by a variety of actors and resources. We have identified the policies, actions and interventions that take place in the local ecosystem but could be implemented by any of the different levels of government involved and, thus, affect the case study. We have then diagnosed the existing policy gaps and provided policy recommendations (See Figure 2).

Figure 2. Rationale of the research process

Source: Own elaboration

In terms of methodology, we have used a two-fold approach: on the one hand, we have deeply analysed the sector reports produced during the CICERONE fieldwork from a policy lens, considering the territorial impact the different GPN phase might have and the corresponding regional and local interventions to enhance or prevent these territorial side effects. (See Table 2 for a list of the CICERONE reports that show the results of the fieldwork).

Table 2. CICERONE reports

Reports
Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Pareja-Eastaway, M., Vidaechea, J., Pradel, M. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from architectural design (CICERONE report D2.1) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884621
Gmeiner, R., Kolokytha, O., Plebańczyk, K. (2023). Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from cultural heritage, archives and libraries (CICERONE report D2.2) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884843
Inno, P., Henriksson, T., Greco, L., d’Ovidio, M. (2022) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the artistic crafts industry (CICERONE report D2.3) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885375
Tomova, B., Andreeva, D., Andreeva, T., Kolokytha, O., Gmeiner, R., Ognyanova, N., Antonova, V., Kirilova, E., (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the audiovisual and radio industry (CICERONE report D2.4) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8016833
D’Ovidio, M., Greco, L., Inno, P., Pareja-Eastaway, M., Pradel, M. and Vidaechea, J. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from fashion design (CICERONE report D2.5) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885540
Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Tomova, B., Andreeva, D. and Kutin, L. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the festival and performing arts industries (CICERONE report D2.6a) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884404
Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Andreeva, D., Tomova, B. and Andreeva, T. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the visuals arts industry (CICERONE report D2.6b) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884221
Henriksson, T. and Janowska, A.A. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the European music industry (CICERONE report D2.7) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885744
Karpińska, A., Ilczuk, D., Cholewicka, E., Bennett, T. and Pratt, A. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the publishing industry (CICERONE report D2.8) https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6886027

On the other hand, we have approached the CICERONE partner leaders and carried out a survey to collect their impressions with respect to the functioning of the local ecosystem observed during the realisation of the CICERONE fieldwork. We aim at identifying policy interventions but also gaps for action. The following questions guided the exchange of information:

- Considering the GPN phases in the xxx sector, is there any phase that clearly receives support or is regulated at the local scale? If so, in which manner (i.e., clustering, promotion of exchange activities, direct support to the organisation/artist, etc.)?
- What do you think would be the 'crystal-clear' gap in the local ecosystem where the public sector might act? What do you think should be considered?
- According to you, which would be the 'building blocks' (i.e., sustainability, competitiveness, labor conditions, etc.) that can be better addressed by the local policies in the xxx sector?
- Any other thing that should be pointed out?

This report stresses the following facts which are aligned with previous CICERONE results:

- 1) The local/regional component is crucial in policy making, consistent with the literature and mentioned in WP1. All value-creating and value-capturing activities are shaped (and constrained) by the regulatory and institutional context. Exploring such contexts involves investigating (labour) laws, IPR, subsidies, tax incentives and other institutional frameworks that affect the structure and activities of the CCIs in their locales.
- 2) Since there is a large variation in production networks – spatial footprint and mode of governance – there is no one-size-fits all set of policies, so generalisation becomes difficult, as it will be stressed in the following section (D 6.1). Consequently, tailor-made policies and ditto interventions are essential, there are certain common elements in policymaking that can be applied in different cases as it has been shown in the CICERONE reports emerging from the empirical fieldwork (See Table 2).
- 3) Although the results in this report are not intended to be a representative set given the large variation of the cases, they exemplify how policies at the local/regional level can impact on production networks. The CICERONE fieldwork presents different typologies of networks and, hence, different needs for policymaking. Our contribution aims to be a roadmap or a set of stages in a stepwise approach to policy making which requires scanning or mapping the production networks which are the object of intervention and which, accordingly, would also imply – in real-life policymaking – the gathering of relevant data.

As we have seen elsewhere in CICERONE, the presence of the CCI can lead to a reshaping of the place itself, as its presence potentially brings positive spill-over effects, such as job opportunities in new agglomerations (Coe, 2015). Anticipating these rewards, CCIs are increasingly seen as tools of local economic development, and policies affecting CCIs exists on all scales. Understanding how these types of incentives shape and are being shaped by the CCI in question, is crucial (Coe, 2015). Analysing the territorial embeddedness of the CCI therefore needs to be multi-scalar, as regulatory frameworks shaping the CCI can be found at both macro-regional, national and local scales.

1. Introduction to local and regional ecosystems and their embeddedness in national frameworks

1.1 The role of 'local' and 'regional' ecosystems in global production networks

As mentioned, the GPN approach does not understand territories merely as a scenario in which firms stay and connect to global networks, but as integral elements contributing to configure the network itself. The local context is relevant as it shapes firms' actions and their capacity to couple with extra-local firms and networks. It also influences the way in which firms from outside the region settle in a territory and relate with local firms. Focusing on creation, CCS research has tended to focus on the central city to analyse dynamics and agglomeration economies to understand local contexts. The local context is understood here in a broader sense: it refers to the functional city represented by the metropolitan region and identifies different local ecosystems around a particular sector, some of them embedded in the urban sphere, some other in different locations such as industrial districts or peripheral neighbourhoods.

How cities and metropolitan regions are connected to the global economy has been extensively analysed. Here we aim to combine the approach on local ecosystems with the GPN approach. According to Manuel Castells, it becomes essential to consider global networks of connectivity to understand the forms of contemporary urbanisation (Castells, 2010). Those networks are diverse but essentially global. The boundaries of the local ecosystem are blurred and depend on the articulation of the network at the geographical scale. *'The key spatial feature of the network society is the networked connection between the local and the global'* (Castells, 2010, p. 2740). Local ecosystems represent the nodes of those networks globally connected. These global networks do not have the same geography, and they not necessary share the same nodes. The local ecosystem is the urban dimension of multi-layered global networks. It entails the overlap in the local arena of different globally connected networks, creating in the geographical space multiple connections and externalities between networks.

While a thriving, competitive local ecosystem would be associated with the spatial scale of multiple global networks, other local ecosystems though, are left outside those networks with organisations and actors with scarce capacity or lack of willingness to globally connect. The landing of these global

networks linked through nodes in specific spatial contexts depends on multiple variables that go from the internationalisation of the companies to the digitalisation of the space. Policy strategies and interventions by multiple actors at the local scale would probably join efforts in becoming part of the global network if it is understood as a competitive drive for the local ecosystem.

Creative ecosystems, creative hubs and creative clusters generate at the local level a dynamic agglomeration of creative firms, talented people and institutions that provide the necessary resources to these creative industries. The idea of a local ecosystem of organisations stems from biology and refers to a community of living organisms that live and interact in a specific environment that can be affected by macro shocks. It is also about multiple order causalities as well as about emergent effects at higher levels of aggregation. In other words, it deals with the connection between actors, places and spaces in a particular territorial context. It has been broadly used on innovation ecosystems literature (Cohendet et al., 2020; Pique et al., 2018). It departs from the idea that organisations do not exist in a vacuum. They attract resources of all sorts, draw on capital, partners suppliers and customers to create cooperative networks (Moore, 1993). Policy actions must consider the actors that compose the local ecosystem, the type of connections established among them, the resources and capabilities needed and the dominant power relations. However, GPN extends the established connections to a higher level, referring to the network between the components of the different phases of the production which are definitely embedded in the local but can reach a global dimension of connectivity.

As GPN focuses on firms and networks of firms, the approach unpacks the relationship between various actors within the production system as a whole, which entail complex combinations of local and non-local connections (Coe, 2015). The global production networks of CCS organisations are anchored in local spaces (ecologies) where the process of creation, production, exchange, distribution and archive does effectively take place determining the global competitiveness of the firm. The GPN approach allows to understand that whatever type of intervention (i.e., national regulations, local stimuli to better education skills, lobbying of stakeholders, etc.) in the local ecosystem will have two different impacts: on the one hand, a global impact in terms of the competitive positioning of the network of these organisations in the global scenario and, changes in the composition of organisations, tensions or agreements in the power relations between actors in the network. On the other, it will also affect the local scenario. It is a bi-directional impact between both dimensions, the local and the network.

In the case of CCS, various stakeholders such as artists, patrons, organisations, institutions, governments, entrepreneurs and sponsors, among others, configure the ecosystem that promotes, supports and develops culture and creativity under the form of different endeavours in a particular place. There is no single model of local ecosystems of CCS as they reflect their intrinsic diverse nature formed by multiple actors with diverse goals and capabilities. Creative ecosystems might be state-driven, market-driven or any other resultant combination of both without forgetting the possible involvement of the community or the audience (Anders-Morawska, 2017). This results in a wide

diversity of approaches at the local arena. In general terms, the CCS exhibit a strong embeddedness in their creative local ecosystems. The GPN approach contributes to the understanding of how this local ecosystem and the CCS embeddedness is challenged by global (supralocal) relations of production.

1.2 The subsidiarity principle and the embeddedness of the local ecosystem in higher (national, European, global) scales

Local ecosystems are related to what the GPN approach defines as spatial embeddedness of global production networks. From a sociological perspective, embeddedness relates to institutional context generating different forms of formal and informal regulation of economic activities and social life. Productive activities in cities enmeshed in a set of informal and formal norms, values and ways of producing which are product of close interaction of local actors, including civil society, private actors and public administration. Local institutional context provides formal regulations on developing activities, some of them developed at higher scales, such as establishing labour conditions, environmental regulations, etc. There are also regulations in relation to quality of products, production processes etc. which are often the result of negotiations with local producers. Local institutional contexts also include norms and values codifying tacit knowledge on creation, production, distribution, exchange, and archiving, as well as environments for the development of different phases of production. Epistemic communities could also be considered as codifiers of tacit knowledge and as part of the local institutional context that is somewhat multilevel as it is also connected globally (Scott, 2000). Local ecosystems can be understood as the network of stakeholders in the CCS, which are immersed in the local institutional context but also, contribute to transform it. In this regard, the local ecosystem is embedded in a wider governance framework, multilevel and multi-scalar: it comprises at the same time different territorial tiers, regional, national or supranational, with a varied degree of relevance in the local policymaking according to the degree of decentralisation of the political system. Formal regulations shaped by different levels of government targeting distinct policy challenges will be specifically configured at the local level depending on singular spatial relations, formal and informal, with close actors in terms of the GPN perspective.

For instance, Next Generation Funds, despite being a European source for funding, have a strong impact in the local ecosystem. These funds are oriented in a general way to support digitalisation and sustainability (recovery and resilience). They are distributed among Member States in the form of grants and loans. Next Generation funds are managed at national level, but many countries are allowing local and regional administrations to apply for funds on sustainability and digitalisation, together with private actors. This could be directed towards the improvement of CCS competitiveness.

In a similar vein, the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) support the development of European partnerships among leading companies, research labs and higher education. They are called, EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities. In June 2022, the Institute launched a new community dedicated to CCS. EIT Culture & Creativity aim is to deliver innovative solutions to help the sectors and industries become stronger and more resilient. This community will train the sector's future entrepreneurs, power its cutting-edge ventures, and deliver innovative solutions to the challenges facing the sectors. It would also *bridge regional innovation gaps* and harness the power of these sectors to support Europe's cultural leadership.

We should stress the uneven role of local institutional context taking into consideration two intertwined variables: if the product is digital or physical, and the degree of globalisation of the sector. These variables might influence the degree of local embeddedness of the sectors.

1.3 Why and how the global production network is dependent on the socio-institutional context for policy-making?

Local ecosystems are key in CCS as creative and cultural economic activities are often organised as communities of practice, forming networks of professionals who cooperate, exchange views and ideas and inform each other about trends of professional, political and practical concern (Lange, Pradel-Miquel, and Garnizov, 2010: 310). Following this definition, policies are aimed at transforming institutional contexts by modifying existing regulations or creating new ones, promoting certain values and norms, fostering interactions between stakeholders and privileging certain actors over others in the processes of policymaking.

However, the GPN approach provides a better understanding of how the network might benefit from the different socio-institutional context where the network is embedded. For instance, the rise of co-productions since the end of the nineties in the film industry is explained by including a wider narrative of financial and institutional dynamics that shape the industrial organisation of companies. Film producers have identified co-productions as an ideal strategy to raise higher budgets by combining sources of soft money from multiple countries. The introduction of tax incentives by governments in Europe, to encourage private investment into film in the context of wider policy has thus led to a vicious circle of tax competition between competition states globally. *'This competition is reinforcing itself, makes production increasingly footloose and encourages co-productions in search for finance'* (Morawetz et al., 2007, p. 434).

In a similar vein, Kerr and Cawley (2012) provide some insights with respect to the case of digital games in Ireland. Most of the growth in employment in the Irish games industry is based in support functions which tend to relocate to regional centres around the world to service regional markets, and are not

grounded in research and development, or content/intellectual property development. It is very difficult in terms of policy action to move up in the value chain towards higher value-added forms of information labour. However, participating in exchange activities in the sector (Developers conferences in US, London or France) contributes to the engagement of Irish organisations in global production networks. *'While the industry has been identified by local and European policy-makers as being among the 'creative industries' that have the potential to drive economic growth and employment creation, our research on the spatialisation politics of the global industry would suggest that technology alone will not be sufficient to overcome the barriers faced by small- to medium-sized companies in peripheral locations'* (Kerr & Cawley, 2012, p. 412).

The Irish games industry has, in our opinion, suffered from a lack of understanding in policy circles of the content generation stage of the value chain and the asymmetrical power relationship between developers and publishers. Currently, both educational programmes and state industrial supports emphasise software and 'technology' driven projects while the local venture capital and non-state funding sources view games as a very risky investment. In this context it is hard to see how strong content development companies can develop in the Irish context.' (Kerr & Cawley, 2012, p. 414)

In short, a narrow focus on spatial clusters limits the understanding of how global dynamics might affect the organisation of the sector.

As co-productions become an integral part of the European film industry, it can become equally important (or even more important) for producers to have international links than it is to be embedded in a national or regional context. By linking producers across borders, increased co-production activity can be seen as restructuring the film industries in Europe that previously operated predominantly in a regional/national context, towards an integrated networked cross-border industry.

1.4 How the spatial footprint of global production networks is relevant for policy recommendations/establishment of policy frameworks?

There has been a devolution of power in certain sectors towards lower levels of government and an increasing role of the private (non-profit) sector for the implementation of cultural policies that might affect the GPN phases, particularly the creation and production.

Policies for CCS have focused on creation (see WP3 deliverables of the CICERONE project). In fact, creative and cultural sectors are often producing elsewhere, using urban agglomerations as spaces for creation and design. Nevertheless, for small companies and self-employed creators, policies can be

oriented to helping them in coupling with other local companies in terms of production, distribution, exchange and archiving. This means widening the policies of clustering beyond the idea of generating a 'creative milieu' or atmospheres in which they interact with other creativity actors.

Example 1: the local influence of global exchange devices. The case of awards in architecture

Architecture is an industry where prizes and awards play a fundamental role in the dissemination of innovation, design and technology. These gatekeepers have become indirect measures of quality of architects and architecture studios: they provide a comprehensive signal in the market that might change the career and popularity of those awarded. As exchange devices, they favour the spread of knowledge among communities. Most of them are internationally valued and have a local impact. (Vriesema et al. 2023a)

Sectors benefit from global/supranational programs that have a direct impact on the local ecosystem. Projects funded, for instance, by Creative Europe, directly impact the local ecosystem, at least in the short run. The problem is the continuity and lack of stability of these projects. The same might apply to the New Generation Funds. Up to what extent: a) they will impact all the phases of the sector? b) will be relatively stable over time? c) what if these funds do not target the local ecosystem as an objective but the global competitiveness? In a similar vein, the European Industrial Renaissance initiative launched by the European Commission establishes a set of principles that are well aligned with the recovery and reinforcement of the local ecosystem. As CCs majorly exhibit a small and medium dimension, support to SMEs in general is well-received in the CCs context. Accelerators, innovation hubs, start-ups, shared infrastructures at an early stage of the company... these are examples of general support to SMEs that also affect the CCs. In general, the territorialisation of policies, or at least its management, at the local level contributes to better target those organisations in need of support.

2. Multilevel policy challenges manifested in the local and regional ecosystems through a production network approach

In the last decades CCS have played a growing role in local and regional economic development strategies of cities in the Global North, giving place to urbanisation and creation of infrastructures, fostering innovation and creativity hubs, developing cultural facilities, and fostering artistic creation, and more generally, generating conditions for interaction as a way to strengthen creative production. Thus, the role of public policies and subsidies has become central in the organisation of creative industries GPNs.

These policies take place in a multi-level governance scheme in which European, national, regional and local levels contribute to establish the regulatory framework. We can find differences between national frameworks in terms of decentralisation and the role of different administrative levels in regulation. Nevertheless, regional and local administrations tend to use their resources available to contribute to develop coupling strategies for creative and cultural companies, and more widely, to engage their city or region in global production networks. Moreover, national governments and the EU have tended to foster these regional strategies with funds on specific programs. Strategic coupling as a ‘mutual dependent and constitutive process involving particular ties, shared interests and cooperation between two or three groups of economic actors’ (Yeung, 2016, p. 54) explains, for instance, trans-local branding strategies can be facilitated by the partnership between local branded firms and the state (Lin, 2021).

This document considers a two-folded perspective in policy challenges: on the one hand, those challenges that refer to the production system (competitiveness, economic development, environmental sustainability and resilience) and, on the other hand, it also reflects social and cultural components of CCS (labour conditions, societal values, etc.). In this section, we will be considering strategic coupling and forms of strategic coupling at different levels of firms, institutions and other actors relevant for the sector.

2.1 Multilevel policy challenges are affected by the diverse characteristics of the cultural and creative sector

CCS are always inserted in a specific socio-institutional frameworks. Two types of actions with respect to policies can be found in the local ecosystem: on the one hand, the local arena is where supranational or national regulations and policies are put in practice. On the other hand, the local level can develop its own policy tools, usually aligned with the goals of higher levels of government but also involving possibilities of conflict.

The extreme diversity of the CCS needs to be considered when analysing the local ecosystem from a multilevel policy perspective. Sectors like the audio-visual are extremely fragmented and small and medium companies overrepresented. However, large companies may coexist. CCS present unequal representation of phases, (i.e., overrepresentation of creation and archive in cultural heritage) (Gmeiner et al. 2023). Sectors like publishing might have a parallel ecosystem completely online (digital publishing ecosystem) (Karpińska et al. 2023). Sectors like music are mainly determined by national and international rules, however there is room for local initiatives to support the sector (Henriksson and Janowska, 2023).

Clustering is relevant for many CCS. Vertical and horizontal integration in the territory of organisations as well as the presence of institutions, research centres, universities or professional organisations are often stimulated from the local government. Different phases of the production network can be found creating a complex ecosystem. However, since organisations might be globally interconnected throughout networks, the cluster perspective in terms of policymaking is limited since it avoids the consideration of these particular global dynamics that acquire a decisive relevance for the competitiveness of the organisations and thus, the local ecosystem. According to Coe (2015): *'a GPN lens allows us to see beyond dynamics of local clustering and territorial embeddedness to reveal broader patterns of network embeddedness, and thereby how 'the forces shaping the industry remain beyond the control and influence of local actors'* (N. Coe, 2015, p. 493)

Example 2: Labour conditions in CCS

CCS require workers with a range of skills (business knowledge, entrepreneurial, management, digital and technical skills) that are often difficult to find in their entirety. For instance, schemes for young graduates to enter the profession or the incentives from local authorities to reside and be professionally active in a certain area (for the case of Videogames) are strategies to increase human capital in CCS. Fostering professionalisation and new forms of organisation of labour can be an indirect approach at the local level on labour conditions for instance recognising an association of designers as legitimate to discuss the promotion of design from the administration.

As Wait and Gibson (2009) point out, strengthening culture and the cultural and creative industries is one of the possibilities for local government to adapt to the new contexts determined by globalisation through: support for emerging artists, encouraging active participation in the arts, opening the arts to a wider public through the organisation of festivals and exhibitions. Thus, special attention is paid

to how the role of creative activity is essential to facilitate a sense of "relevance" and "community" through the promotion of social relations in streets, parks and neighbourhoods. In a similar vein, since CCS are responsible for huge spillovers as activities linked to art, culture and creative industries have a wider impact on the territory and society or the economy through the overflow of concepts, ideas, skills, knowledge and different types of capital' (Tom Fleming Creative Consultancy, 2015, p. 15) fostering CCS becomes of particular interest in policy action terms.

Example 3: Power relations in publishing sector

There is a significant power imbalance between publisher and author and hence an asymmetrical relationship. Retailers generally gain a larger slice of the purchase price; with digitisation the publishers have gained a larger proportion of earnings leaving the authors worse off and with little bargaining power. It is only recently that the organisation of the publishing industry has become visible to research and policy; notably, through the new deals that have been taking place as a process of dis- and re- integration of publishing. The closure of printing plants, and the loss of local employment in printing and distribution has passed with little comment. As has the loss of a cultural institution, the high street bookshop, and in some countries the public library. Likewise, the cuts in research budgets for universities, and the funding of their libraries. These are the very foundation of reading and writing, and scientific, culture. Need to stress the cultural and economic value of CCs. (Karpińska et al. 2023)

Example 4: The relevance/vulnerability of the creator

A large part of the creative industries is developed in realms or domains that appear to be less regulated such as labour conditions or the quality of the product and on a very small scale based basically on the talent creativity or skills of an individual. The potential of these industries is very high and local policies have the chance to promote creativity as the original source for them. One of the sectors most vulnerable to the lack of support for the development of their creativity are artists. In this sense measures aimed at:

1. obtaining funding on an individual or project basis.
2. grants for training.
3. grants for artists' associations to guarantee their representativeness.
4. regulation of authors' rights to guarantee the future profitability of their creations to accompany the visibility of the sector and the coverage of its most important needs.

Since the characteristics of CCS reflects an overrepresentation of micro, small and medium organisations, policies and actions supporting them, despite the predominant phase in which they are working, is a common issue. Clustering in the territory to enhance and promote synergies among companies, strengthening SME support for protecting their IP and for internationalisation, improving

their access to soft finance and developing policy dialogues with key trade partners, are examples of this type of support. The SBA (Small Business Act) reflects in the first principle ‘the creation of an environment in which entrepreneurs and family businesses can thrive and entrepreneurship is rewarded’.

The degree of modernisation and digitalisation of CCS varies strongly within each sector and among them. It affects all phases of the production network. While some sectors such as architecture, videogames and up to a certain extent, cultural heritage, have been fast in their adequation to new technologies, others like crafts are less advanced in this transformation.

CCS are fertile soil for partnerships between public and private actors. The cutbacks in public expenditure have affected the local government since 2008. The organisation of cultural activities, for instance, festivals of all kinds, traditionally in hands of the local government, has been progressively shifted to partnerships with other actors or even completely left in private hands.

2.2 Global production network phases and strategic coupling in a multilevel policy framework

Looking at the different phases of production of the GPN allows to detect needs and possible policies to foster the coupling of firms to different parts of the production network. As stated above, policies on creative and cultural sectors have tended to focus on the creation phase, looking for the emergence of new firms designing/creating new products or services. Departing from our analysis of production networks in the creative and cultural sectors, we can find some features in the other phases that deserve attention and that can orient local policies.

Creation

The creation phase emerges as the most vulnerable and in need of protection and support. The artist as an object of policy in the local ecosystem is supported by different schemes that aim not only at protecting the creator but also at encouraging creative production by means of education, mentorship, and finance. This is the case, for instance, of the publishing sector in London (Karpińska et al., 2023).

Mobility across countries or cities is a common activity for creators to enrich their experiences, exchange knowledge and gain reputation. Many general programs, not specific for CCS, at the local level are oriented in this direction.

A variety of key actors emerges in this phase: from institutional (formal) endeavours to support artistic creation to patronage and crowdfunding platforms. Foundations, associations and intergovernmental bodies are an intrinsic part.

In the cultural heritage sector and up to a certain extent, in archives and libraries, besides the traditional tools such as tax incentives or grants, the promotion of the site or the intangible tradition, the recognition of its value by means of workshops, leaflets, conferences, etc. is part of the creation phase.

Fostering creativity leading to new products, materials, processes and business models in the fashion sector is another example of supporting the emergent fashion designers and their commitment with innovation and new added value production (D'Ovidio et al., 2023).

Wirtschaftsagentur Wien for example, finances videogame entrepreneurs and organises network activities (that also reinforces the exchange phase) to strengthen the local industry. MA7, the subsidies department of the city of Vienna, is also actively involved in supporting local professionals.

Production

Along the production phase, the local ecosystem or the city brand where it takes place might contribute to the positive (or negative) reputation of the output. Depending on the characteristics of the sector, support for SMEs and entrepreneurship might be extremely important. For instance, in the case of Publishing, a sector with a mix of a few large companies and a large number of small firms, this type of support is not excessively relevant. However, in the Crafts sector, backing the small entrepreneurs is crucial (Inno et al., 2023).

The protection and preservation of cultural heritage, owned by the public sector under the form of trusts, departments, agencies, etc. is a form of intervention as the decision to launch and support new libraries or archives in the local ecosystem (Gmeiner et al., 2023).

A possible pathway to improve the local ecosystem in the production phase is the 'anticipation' of required skills. Programs and grants oriented to develop the quality and adequacy of the labour force are crucial in this phase. Educational and vocational training as well as raising awareness for labour opportunities represent an extraordinarily added value to the young generation with respect to the requirements of the CCs. This is the case, for instance, of the fashion design industry (D'Ovidio et al., 2023).

Access to local intermediate (ancillary) goods, rather than having to import them, could be relevant in certain cases. For instance, domestic materials and components are important for crafts, but also to fashion or architecture.

Patronage and sponsoring of cultural activities have substituted direct public funding. This is the case of festivals, where the private initiative has entered strongly into the market, not only in the creation phase but across production and distribution.

The production phase is often supported by the local government based on calls for projects. This is the case, for instance, of Sofia, where the municipality directly supports the filming process when the film is shot in the city by waiving the specialized fees. The appearance of these two types of support reflects the fact that Sofia has been a UNESCO City of Film since 2014 which connects with the exchange phase in the sector (Vriesema et al., 2003c)

Exchange

The local ecosystem is present in the exchange phase by means of organising festivals, fairs, workshops, exhibitions or catwalks where the creative production is shown, and the specialised communities can meet and transfer knowledge and ideas. Taking part in an international network such as the Creative Cities Network of the UNESCO is an indirect form to align local reputations (and knowledge) in a global context. For instance, the main task of each of the Cities of Literature is to create and implement a program to promote literary heritage, popularize reading among residents and support the local book market. In a similar vein, the Municipality of Sofia supports the Sofia International Film Festival throughout a direct subsidy, as well as all film festivals that are on the territory of the city and are part of the Cultural Calendar of the city.

Example 5: Festivals and fairs as catalysers for coupling

Festivals and fairs are mechanisms that provide an adequate environment to couple from the local to the global or to attract global, powerful actors. Or both, simultaneously. They have also a role in distribution. The understanding of their relevance as devices of knowledge exchange and gatekeepers in many sectors connects the local ecosystem to higher levels of the production network. (Vriesema et al., 2023b)

Guaranteeing the consumption or the access to all no matter race or economic situation is an indirect form of intervention by public authorities that supports the exchange phase of Cultural Heritage. Libraries and Archives (Gmeiner et al., 2023).

Alliances between cities as it is the case of United Cities and Local Governments (UCLG) or UNESCO Creative Cities do influence the local ecosystem throughout promoting partnerships and agreements between stakeholders at the local level. Heritage, for instance, has been part of larger urban regeneration programs allowing cities to become more attractive. In these cases, culture as a tool of transformation plays a key role.

One of characteristics of CCs in the exchange phase is the presence of key stakeholders that may act as gatekeepers but also as a source of value exchange. This is the case of Schools of Architecture, always context based. Related to first, the harmonisation of education programs, regulations and requirements to become an architect in the European Union is the starting point for a European competitiveness of the profession. This is also the case of music schools at the local level which usually receive a strong support by the municipality (Henriksson and Janowska, 2023).

At the local level, cultural heritage support is most often provided on the exchange phase. For example, the Lesser Poland Cultural Heritage Days, i.e., opening places that are difficult to access on a daily basis, activities around - is a cyclical project. Similarly, the activities like open museums days. This means that heritage is "used" to promote the region.

In publishing, programmes related to the promotion of reading, e.g., public campaigns (outdoor advertising, reading books on the radio, advertisements in the media), publicly funded book and reading festivals, are mainly supported by municipalities, but also by ministries (Karpińska et al., 2023).

Distribution

The distribution phase of CCIs in general adopts online and onsite forms. Products can be sold in the local environment but usually also in the global market through fairs or online platforms. Local ecosystems can contribute to the distribution of products by organising fairs (The Book Fair in London) generating bidirectional externalities between the city and the sector. Local campaigns addressed to consume creative products are supposed to enhance the acquisitions by the customers (Karpińska et al., 2023).

The Cultural Heritage, Archives and Libraries Sector is probably one of the most attached to the local ecosystem. Interestingly, despite the common relevance in all sectors of supralocal support, in the Cultural Heritage Sector there has been a devolution of power to lower levels of government and an increasing role of the private (non-profit) sector for the implementation of cultural policies (Gmeiner et al., 2023).

For instance, in the audio-visual sector, structural support might be provided for cinemas, very much at risk after the emergence of online distribution of movies and the pandemic effect (covering or eliminating fixed costs, such as rent, taxes, etc.) (Tomova et al., 2023).

Local authorities play a paramount role- such as for example Vienna Tourism Board or the district board of the 19th District where many Heurigen regulating the way the Heurigen work such as for example with regards to health/ food - related regulations (Gmeiner et al., 2023).

Local fairs for the craft sector are heavily supported by the municipality. This type of support may act in both the exchange and distribution phase. Similarly, projects that promote the consumption of cultural goods at the local scene do receive support from the local government as one of the key stakeholders in the context. This is the case of the Cinema in the Neighbourhood project, where screenings are made in open urban spaces in Sofia and the municipality is one of the partners for this initiative (Inno et al.,2023).

Archiving

Finally, the archive phase, can represent physical collections of designs, products and processes. The future Barcelona Museum of Architecture, directly supported by the municipality but also involving other crucial actors such as the School of Architecture or the Catalanian Associations of Architects is meant to be one of the most important archives in the sector, internationally speaking (Vriesema et al., 2023a)

3. Using the typology: case illustrations related to production network types

As explained in the introduction, the typology serves as an analytical tool to identify the key actors and stakeholders, spatial levels of involvement, and power structures within production networks. Its goal is to provide a conceptual framework to understand the different types of production networks that exist in regions, sectors, or industries, and to devise effective policy interventions to address economic, social, cultural, or environmental challenges.

The typology includes eight ideal-types of production networks organized around two variables: the spatial footprint and the governance model. The positioning of the Cicerone cases follows on the table below.

Table 2. The typology case distribution

		Governance structure (Coordination of the production network at network level)	
		Multiple lead actors	Single lead actor
Spatial footprint	Local/ regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Festivals and performing arts (Amalyashi Festival) - Cultural heritage (Wiener heurigenkultur) - Architecture (MEF Architect) - Visuals arts (Simbumski and UNU Rotterdam; Patty Morgan) - Artistic crafts (Prisma) - Music (independent debutant artist) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Architecture (Theater Zuidplein) - Artistic craft (Swedish glass making)
	National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Artistic craft (Konsthantverkarna) - Heritage (Jagiellonian University Museum Collegium Maius) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Libraries and archives (Archiv Österreichischer Popularmusik)
	Intra-EU		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Festivals and performing arts (Varna Summer Festival)
	Extra-EU/ Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fashion design (Magenta Co; Cyan Co) - Visuals arts (Vienna gaming company) - Publishing (STM Publishing) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Festivals and performing arts (Lowlands Festival; Nederlands Dans Theater) - Audiovisual and radio (KLAS Film production company; Euroradio; Eurovision) - Design (Yellow Co) - Architecture (Guallart Architects and Picharchitects) - Visual arts (Venice Biennale) - Publishing (Wisława Szymborska) - Music (Marcin Wasilewski Trio)

There is a clear case distribution with regards to their production networks with two poles. On the one hand, local and regional GPNs show a horizontal governance structure, with multiple lead actors. On the other, single lead actor distributions of power tend to present a global spatial footprint. Furthermore, among CICERONE's case studies there is scarcity of European spatial footprints and an absence of national ones. These patterns suggest that while CCS is a broad and diverse category, there are underlying processes that shape how power and geographical scope are combined.

The single lead actor with a global footprint network type has eleven cases belonging to several culture and creative sectors, including architectural design, publishing, visual arts, artistic crafts, or fashion design, among others. It is the most populated category. The second most representative category is the horizontal and local production network that consists of nine cases, also encompassing several sectors like visual arts, music industry, architectural design, artistic crafts, or cultural heritage.

Policies identified in the most common combination, single actor governance structure and global spatial footprint, are varied and span many different areas: promoting collaboration between firms, supporting education and training, aiding during times of crisis, and so on. These policies can strengthen the production network and promote the expansion of the creative and cultural industries, such as the craft glass manufacturing industry of the glass factory case. While in this case, the policies stem from different levels of government in others the main source is the national authorities. Such is the case of the Bulgarian Ministry of Culture regarding the Bulgarian participation in the Venice Biennale, A prestigious international platform for visual arts. According to the analysis performed on this matter, the policy approach should be strategic and sustainable, with yearly state budget allocations for the Biennale to secure all phases of the project, including preparatory stages of creation and production.

The large architecture practice's project production network serves to illustrate another policy characteristic found in the single lead actor and global spatial footprint typology category. The main policy intervention that arises from the case is the public commission of construction or urban planning projects, where administrations play a critical role as a policy driver in the projects of market-oriented firms. While the firm is based in a European city, the project production network expands several continents, and the lead actor is located in China. There may be room for increasing awareness regarding economic and fiscal dimensions of the evolution towards a circular economy across different levels of policy making. Several potential local policies can be implemented, including increasing public investment in construction or urban planning projects, promoting sustainable and circular architectural practices, and creating an economic and fiscal framework for sustainable construction.

Two out of the three fashion design cases belong to the global spatial footprint with the horizontal governance structure type. The Magenta Co case analyses the GPN of a collection from a sustainable and slow fashion brand while Cyan Co refers to the first collection of an emergent designer. At the local and regional level, Magenta Co case study shows that the value of the product is not only linked

to its quality but also to its sustainability and branding. Sustainability affects the geographical location of the production network in different ways. Network embeddedness is relevant as maintaining relationships between providers and producers involves more than just costs, such as the quality of jobs and environmental principles. Know-how and the capacity to develop designs are also critical to the network's participation, and it can bring some relocation to Europe with fewer environmental costs, if the local production and know how conditions can be fostered through policy interventions. Moreover, local and regional policies to promote sustainability in fashion must focus on production and new forms of distribution and consumption, which may have a multi-level approach. Since the collection's production network has a global spatial footprint extra-local levels of policy intervention are relevant.

Also belonging to fashion design, the typology matrix of Cyan Co's production network provides valuable insights for policy interventions at the local and regional level. First, the horizontal distribution of power in the production network highlights the need for policies that empower emerging designers and provide them with access to resources and support. This could include funding, mentorship programs, and networking opportunities to help them build their cultural, social, and economic capital. Secondly, the local nature of the design and production phases suggests the importance of supporting local production networks and promoting regional economic development. This could involve policies that incentivize local production and provide support for small-scale producers and workshops. It could also involve initiatives that promote sustainable production practices and encourage the use of locally sourced materials. Thirdly, to support the growth on the distribution of the first collection there is a need for policies that promote international trade and facilitate access to global markets for emerging designers and therefore strengthening the designer's power along the network. This could include initiatives that support e-commerce platforms, provide export assistance, and help emerging designers navigate international trade regulations. Finally, the role of intermediaries and sites of exchange in the distribution and exchange phases suggests the importance of policies that support the development of specialized circuits and provide opportunities for emerging designers to showcase their work. This could include initiatives that support fashion weeks, exhibitions, and other events that bring together emerging designers and industry professionals.

The European spatial footprint is represented by two cases. While the Marcin Wasilewski Trio falls under the horizontal governance category, the Varna Summer International Theatre Festival operates under a single lead actor power configuration. A major international theatre event, its organisation is carried out by the ViaFest Foundation with the joint support of the Municipality of Varna and the Bulgarian Ministry of Culture. The Marcin Wasilewski Trio shares the power with the recording label and the band's manager.

CICERONE's case studies are distributed according to their production network's spatial footprint and the governance. The single lead actor with a global footprint and the horizontal governance with local/regional dimension typologies are the two most common. However, there is a scarcity of

production networks with European spatial footprints and an absence of national ones, indicating a potential new line of inquiry on the CCS.

4. Conclusions and policy recommendations from the local ecosystem in a multilevel governance perspective

Local and regional policies to foster CCS have tended to focus on generating the environment and institutional conditions to promote creativity and entrepreneurship. Local policies have combined soft and hard factors to attract ‘talent’ (understood as skilled professionals) and investments. The aim has been to reinforce local ecosystems for creation, and specific policies have focused on creating the urban environment, stimulating cultural sectors through public action and promoting agglomeration economies of strategic sectors. As we have seen in Power & Kloosterman (2023), an approach based on Global Production Networks provides a different perspective and allows for a new set of policy instruments. GPN approach aims to analyse how production of goods and services are increasingly based on a network of companies and actors that are globally scattered and how this contributes to uneven territorial development. Nevertheless, the approach is not only explaining the impact of companies in territories but the complex interactions between local production systems and global production networks. Institutional actors in territories can be considered as part of the network, and institutional contexts influence on how the network is shaped as the network influences the territory.

This is especially true in the case of CCS, in which public administrations not only generate regulations and conditions but also contribute often to different phases of the production process as actors, funding, hiring or actively generating part of the process. Thus, the GPN approach considers two different elements that bring possibilities for new local and regional policies for CCS. On the one hand, CCS are understood in a wider sense, including different activities and phases of the production, assessing where value is captured. On the other hand, taking into consideration the networked organisation of production, firms and activities are coupled (or not) to wider networks and their potential development. Identifying the representation of CCS in the European scenario provides a clear understanding of the potential these organisations might have if they work aligned (KEA European Affairs, 2023).

Departing from the empirical fieldwork of CICERONE, we have detected possible policy approaches to foster strategic coupling of companies and territories in GPNs in the CCS. Despite some of them are not new policies, the GPN approach allows for better targeting the objectives of such policies. For instance, many cities and regions try to develop their own events to exhibit works in the CCS as a large event usually attracts such sectors strengthening endogenous growth. Nevertheless, we detected that a more modest policy based on local support to creators in terms of exchange in extra-local contexts

(exhibiting their works and interacting with extra-local sectors) could be relevant to ensure their strategic coupling and their growth, and at the same time this can promote the territory. In a similar vein, local and regional administration can play a role in connecting creators with local industrial producers. This generates new synergies between industry-related and creative actors. This can be complemented with support to his local network in terms of distribution and exchange, ensuring its strategic coupling with extra-local (global) networks.

Thus, fostering new forms of association and collaboration between different local actors can be a way not only to strengthen the local ecosystem but also to generate conditions for strategic coupling to wider networks. As we have seen, promoting the growth of emerging firms and creators through helping them in generating a network for production, distribution, and exchange phases is key. This is a first step to consolidate networks based on multiple lead actors and local/regional spatial footprint. For larger, established companies, new forms of collaboration to fostering their activity might contribute to upgrading the role of such companies in the global production network (becoming leading firms or having a significant role in one or several part of the production process). This is a key contribution of applying a production network to CCS in the design and effectiveness of policy making (Kloosterman, 2023).

In summary, local and regional policies can go beyond promoting local ecosystems focusing on strategic coupling. Fostering the local ecosystem is relevant and a necessary part of local policies for CCS, as it allows creation, generates regulations that help creation process and bring the possibilities for collaboration and interaction between local actors. Nevertheless, this can be complemented with policies to couple actors and parts of the production taking place in these ecosystems to wider networks and extra-local actors in different stages of the production process. Policies fostering distribution and exchange in different ways (digitalisation, networking with actors at other scales) are key as they allow to capture value at the local level. From a territorial perspective, the GPN approach provides new mid-term strategies for territories beyond the general aim of attracting activities allowing for the territory to become specialized in parts of the production process (production, exchange, distribution). Institutional contexts and economic traditions can help in aligning these objectives.

5. Summary of results

1. How local and regional policies can foster strategic coupling for CCS firms? How can territories reinforce their centrality in Creative and Cultural Sectors GPNs?

In a multi-level context:

- Policies directed at strategic coupling are multi-level, with a relevant role for European regulations and programs. National regulations are still salient, especially in some sectors.
- European policies influence local and regional development, especially in more decentralised countries. Role of different programs and funds that can be used at local regional level.
- Extra-local policies and regulations pave the way for certain strategies for coupling. For instance, favouring flexible but insecure labour markets at national level allows for the landing of some sectors but prevent others to root in cities. For instance, large foreign companies might benefit from the flexible labour market in a particular territory locating their production phase impeding the development of other forms of labour. National cultural policies excluding/including some sectors influence the possibilities for coupling.
- In the same vein, economic growth models and the power of non-creative and cultural sectors can influence the possibilities for these sectors to grow or influence the direction in which they grow. For instance, tourism can shape audiences and products of some CCS producing locally for visitors' consumption and can prevent investments in these sectors as there are more profitable activities.

Two types of local and regional strategies: local/regional coupling (clustering, fostering agglomeration through cooperation between existing actors) and upgrading (strategic coupling with GPNs):

- Clustering has been based on promoting endogenous growth and agglomeration through different strategies. A classic approach has been for local institutions to seek for the anchoring of an established actor in the GPN to connect their local ecosystem: attracting large companies, events etc. to ensure the emergence of new firms and the connection of already existing ones to the network.
- Nevertheless, despite self-employed creators and small companies need support at the local level to couple with other local or regional actors (clustering), they need support also to find their way to couple with other actors at greater scales. Support for

internationalisation such as presentation of work in international events or finding partners to sell in new markets are key.

The efforts on local clustering and upgrading are not incompatible. So, not only policies should be directed to foster clustering but also to ensure strategic coupling. Looking at the dynamics in the different phases can help to find new ways to combine both strategies.

2. How can phases of the production network be considered for policy recommendations?

To understand the complex needs of local firms in terms of local clustering and upgrading, it is useful to look at the phases of the production network, and the actors involved in each phase. Through this analysis, we can detect needs and possible policy approaches to foster CCS through strategic coupling.

There are two caveats in this analysis:

1. There are clear differences between CCS, as they have different degrees of globalisation and territorial embeddedness.
2. In many sectors there is an overlap between different phases; for instance, creation is related to possibilities of production and producers might intervene technically in the process of creation and even in the exchange phase (which can influence the final design).

The analysis of CCS through the GPN lens brings the following findings in terms of policy gaps and policies being developed (see Table 3).

Table 3. Policies by phases based on gaps and best practices detected in CICERONE’s empirical analyses (as part of WP2)

Phase	Policies
Creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local coupling, fostering local environment. - Support to creators/small companies - Fostering the role of tradition in creation (in certain sectors) - Networking, reinforcing the role of communities of practices
Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anticipation of required skills - Fostering reputation of the output of production through branding (traditions) - Fostering collaboration between industrial sectors and CCS (i.e. crafts, design, heritage) - Calls for projects

Exchange	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organising workshops, catwalks, festivals, fairs - Facilitating the access of extra-local events to local actors - Promoting the role of gatekeepers that allow for strategic coupling (i.e., schools of architecture, music schools, film academies)
Distribution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fairs and events for distribution - Campaigns for consumption of creative products - Promoting online and onsite channels of distribution
Archiving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foster public/private local archiving of creative and cultural production as institutions that can collaborate in creation (architecture, design, film, crafts libraries/museums)

3. How do interactions between local economic development and strategic coupling along the GPN promote CCS?

- Using local institutional context and historical trajectories/traditions to foster CCS and local coupling can be a way to open possibilities for coupling at larger scale. It can bring quality branding for the product as well as prestige and rebranding for the territory.

Example: using the textile industrial tradition to produce highly intensive design, sustainable fashion brings sustainability and itself and territorial rebranding from obsolete textile manufacturing to good quality, design-intensive, proximity and environmentally friendly production.

- Role of the territory and its tradition in branding the CCS products or not influences distribution and the role of policies in this. It is clear in Heritage, crafts, design, architecture... but less relevant in videogames, film.

6. Bibliography

- Braun, E., & Lavanga, M. (2007). *An international comparative quick scan of national policies for creative industries*. Euricur. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/254920319>
- Castells, M. (2010). Globalisation, Networking, Urbanisation: Reflections on the Spatial Dynamics of the Information Age. *Urban Studies*, 47(13), 2737–2745. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042098010377365>
- Coe, N. (2015). Global Production Networks in the Creative Industries. In C. Jones, M. Lorenzen, & S. Jonathan (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Creative Industries*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199603510.001.0001>
- Coe, N. M., Hess, M., Yeung, H. W., Dicken, P., Coe, N. M., Hess, M., Yeung, H. W., Dicken, P., & Henderson, J. (2004). 'Globalizing' Regional Development: A Global Production Networks Perspective Published by: Wiley on behalf of The Royal Geographical Society (with the Institute of British Geographers) Stable URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3804369> 'Globalizing'. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 29(4), 468–484.
- Coe, N. M., & Yeung, H. W. (2015). *Global Production Networks: Theorizing Economic Development in an Interconnected World*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198703907.001.0001>
- Cohendet, P., Simon, L., & Mehouachi, C. (2020). From business ecosystems to ecosystems of innovation: the case of the video game industry in Montréal. *Industry and Innovation*, 00(00), 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2020.1793737>
- D'Ovidio, M., Greco, L., Inno, P., Pareja-Eastaway, M., Pradel, M. and Vidaechea, J. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from fashion design (CICERONE report D2.5) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885540>
- European Commission. (2022). *Recovery and Resilience scoreboard. Thematic analysis. Culture and Creative industries*.
- Food, J. (2009). Strategies for creative industries: an international review. *Creative Industries Journal*, 1(2), 91–113. https://doi.org/10.1386/cij.1.2.91_1
- Gmeiner, R., Kolokytha, O., Plebańczyk, K. (2023). Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from cultural heritage, archives and libraries (CICERONE report D2.2) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884843>
- Henriksson, T. and Janowska, A.A. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the European music industry (CICERONE report D2.7) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885744>
- Inno, P., Henriksson, T., Greco, L., d'Ovidio, M. (2022) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the artistic crafts industry (CICERONE report D2.3) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6885375>
- Jeffcutt, P. (2004). Knowledge Relationships and Transactions in a Cultural Economy: Analysing the Creative Industries Ecosystem. *Media International Australia*, 112(1), 67–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878x0411200107>

- Jeffcutt, P., & Pratt, A. C. (2002). Managing creativity in the cultural industries. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 11(4), 225–233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8691.00254>
- Karpińska, A., Ilczuk, D., Cholewicka, E., Bennett, T. and Pratt, A. (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the publishing industry (CICERONE report D2.8) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6886027>
- KEA European Affairs (2023) Cultural and creative sector representation for better policymaking (CICERONE deliverable D6.3) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8061321>
- Kerr, A., & Cawley, A. (2012). The spatialisation of the digital games industry: Lessons from Ireland. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 18(4), 398–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2011.598515>
- Kloosterman, R.C. (2023) Lessons learned from applying a production network-based policy framework to the cultural and creative sector (CICERONE deliverable D6.4) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8098785>
- Lin, C. Y. (2021). State Strategy in the Trans-Local Branding of a Creative Industry Cluster: A Case Study of the Product Design Industry in Taipei. *Tijdschrift Voor Economische En Sociale Geografie*, 112(3), 274–287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tesg.12463>
- Moore, J. F. (1993). Predators and prey: a new strategy of competition. In *Harvard Business Review* (Vol. 71, Issue 3, pp. 75–86).
- Morawetz, N., Hardy, J., Haslam, C., & Randle, K. (2007). Finance, policy and industrial dynamics - The rise of co-productions in the film industry. *Industry and Innovation*, 14(4), 421–443. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662710701524072>
- Pique, J. M., Berbegal-Mirabent, J., & Etzkowitz, H. (2018). Triple Helix and the evolution of ecosystems of innovation: the case of Silicon Valley. In *Triple Helix* (Vol. 5, Issue 1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40604-018-0060-x>
- Power, D. and Kloosterman, R.C. (2023) Policy frameworks for production networks in the creative and cultural sector (CICERONE deliverable D6.1) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8098868>
- Scott, A. J. (1999). The cultural economy: Geography and the creative field. *Media, Culture and Society*, 21(6), 807–817. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016344399021006006>
- Scott, A. J. (2004). Cultural-products industries and urban economic development: Prospects for growth and market contestation in global context. *Urban Affairs Review*, 39(4), 461–490. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1078087403261256>
- Tom Fleming Creative Consultancy. (2015). *Cultural and creative spillovers in Europe: Report on preliminary evidence review* (Issue October).
- Tomova, B., Andreeva, D., Andreeva, T., Kolokytha, O., Gmeiner, R., Ognyanova, N., Antonova, V., Kirilova, E., (2023) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the audiovisual and radio industry (CICERONE report D2.4) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8016833>
- Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Pareja-Eastaway, M., Vidaechea, J., Pradel, M.(2023a) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from architectural design (CICERONE report D2.1) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884621>
- Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Tomova, B., Andreeva, D. and Kutin, L. (2023b) Production networks in the cultural and creative sector: case studies from the festival and performing arts industries (CICERONE report D2.6a) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884404>
- Vriesema, M., Kloosterman, R.C., Van Kempen, S., Andreeva, D., Tomova, B. and Andreeva, T. (2023c) Production networks in the cultural and creative sectors: case studies from the visuals arts industry (CICERONE report D2.6b) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6884221>
- Yeung, H. W. C. (2016). Chapter 3. In H. W. C. Yeung (Ed.), *Strategic Coupling: East Asian Transformation in the New Global Economy*. Cornell University Press.